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A Guide to Different Types of Academic Citation Styles

 Ashley Martin · Sep 7 · 2 min read

Citations help you avoid plagiarism charges and let the readers trace the authentic source easily. There are several types of citation styles, and knowing all the rules by heart can be difficult. But what if you end up using an [APA citation generator](#) for free to create Oxford citations?

Unless you know the rules of the various citation styles, you will not be able to determine whether or not a **reference generator for APA** style is producing the correct answers. On that note, below are some of the most used citation styles with their examples.

1. MLA

Founded by the Modern Language Association, this style is used in the fields of Humanities. When using an [MLA citation generator](#), make sure that results look like this:

In-text: (Hugh and Benson 23)

Bibliography: Hugh, Dave and Todd Benson. The World of Social Media. New York Press, 2011.

2. APA

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parenthetical citation in the format of the author-date system.

In-text citation: (Hugh & Benson, 2011, p. 23).

Bibliography: Hugh, D and Benson, T. (2011). *The World of Social Media*. Berkeley, USA New York Press.

3. Chicago

The Chicago style can be used as footnotes or endnotes by students of history. If you are a science student, you must use the parenthetical style in the author-date format within the text.

In-text citation: *The sentence or data that you have taken from a book*. 1

Bibliography: Hugh, Dave and Todd Benson. *The World of Social Media*. Berkeley: New York Press, 2011.

4. Harvard

Harvard referencing style is used in the field of business and economics. Like APA style, this style is also based on an author-date system. However, do not make the mistake of using an **APA citation generator for free** to cite your paper in the Harvard style.

In-text citation: (Hugh and Benson, 2011, p. 23).

Bibliography: Hugh, D. and Benson, T. (2011) *The World of Social Media*. Berkeley: New York Press.

5. Vancouver

Used in medical fields, this particular style follows a numeric format, where a number within the text indicates the source. The full details of the source are listed in the reference list.

In-text citation: *The sentence or data that you have taken from a book* (1)

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Use this guide the next time you are confused about which citation style to use. Get the format right and then go ahead and use an MLA or APA reference maker.

Reference: *Essay writer online*

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